

Title: 18 Year Old Revolutionizing The Payment Processing Industry

Name: Adam Silverman

Affiliation: CMO at Spot Systems.

INTRODUCTION:

Adam is a serial entrepreneur, and cryptocurrency investor who specialized in business development. Adam is in charge of growing spot systems by utilizing the latest growth hacking methods. Adam is an expert in digital marketing and will use his background to gain attention for Spot Systems.

AIM:

To teach people how to utilizing marketing to grow a crypto currency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Using the latest growth hacking method I am capable of scaling businesses at an unprecedented level.

RESULTS:

Garnering investments for Spot Systems and effectively marketing it through different channels.

CONCLUSIONS:

Looking to teach other individuals about Block chain and teach them how to utilize it to benefit their business.

KEYWORDS:

Marketing, Sales, Entrepreneurship, Business Development.

BIOGRAPHY:

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